

Introduction: Against all odds - labour activism in the Middle East and North Africa

Peyman Jafari

If class politics and labour activism in the West have been relegated to the margins of academic research and public debate in the last two decades, they have been almost entirely ignored when it comes to the analysis of the Middle East. Hence the awarding of the 2015 Nobel Peace Prize to Tunisia's National Dialogue Quartet, in which the Tunisian General Labour Union (UGTT) is the leading force with over a half million members, is one of the rare moments the labour movement in the Middle East has received public recognition, albeit in a partial and distorted manner. As Joel Beinin, the eminent historian of labour in Egypt, recently commented, "most of the international media...followed the [Nobel Prize] committee's lead in constructing a narrative that ignored the leading role of the UGTT in the Quartet and the intense social struggle that forced Ennahda from power."¹ Moreover, the Nobel committee "sanitized" the Tunisian Revolution by stressing "peaceful dialogue" and "consensus-based solutions" and excluding the role of labour struggles in the form strikes, sit-ins, and occupations that fuelled the political transformations.²

Denial of the significance of labour activism and its "sanitization" have a long history, of course. The mode of knowledge production, in the West as well as in the

¹ Ennahda is a moderate Islamist party that won the elections in October 2011 (37%), nine months after a revolutionary movement that had started in mid-December 2010 had ousted president Zine El-Abidine Ben Ali. After Ennahda formed a government, protests continued, including hundreds of strikes and occupations by UGTT. When two leftist political leaders were assassinated by a Salafist group in February and July 2013, the UGTT reacted with general strikes and demonstrations, pushing Ennahda towards compromise with the Quartet (formed in late August 2013). In January 2014 a new government was formed and a new constitution guaranteeing equal civil rights and acknowledging Islam as the country's official religion was adopted.

² Beinin, Joel, "Sanitizing the Tunisian Revolution," 12 October 2015, retrievable at <http://stanfordpress.typepad.com/blog/2015/10/sanitizing-the-tunisian-revolution.html#more>

Middle East, has played its part. In the West, Orientalist essentialism has reduced various social and political aspects of the Middle East to a particular understanding of Islam, obscuring the role of social class. In the Middle East, this approach has been introduced by colonial agents as well as self-Orientalizing intellectuals, but the major contributors to this trend have been the two most influential political projects of the twentieth century in the region, nationalist and Islamist populism.³

From the 1920s onwards, various nationalist populist leaders attempted, often in a post-colonial context, to craft a notion of “the people.” Writing about the Kemalists who laid the foundation of modern Turkey, Erik Zürcher notes “their denial of class struggle, their calling for national solidarity and their ruthless suppression of class-based organizations...”⁴ The same could be said about the nationalism of Kemal Atatürk’s Iranian counterpart Reza Shah. Although less of a populist, he also cracked down on Iran’s growing labour movement in the 1920s and 1930s as part of his passive revolution aimed at industrializing the country from above.⁵ In the 1960s and 1970s, his son, Mohammad Reza Pahlavi, added populist rhetoric and institutions to his father’s nationalist modernization project, stressing the importance of workers’ contribution to the nation and attempting to incorporate them through yellow trade unions.

Similar processes were visible in the Arab countries, where varieties of nationalism combined industrialization and populism through corporatist arrangements, material concessions, and symbolic gestures to incorporate workers and other subaltern groups in grand state-building projects. In the early 20th century, most workers were working as servants or were occupied in small shops, weaving cotton or carpets, spinning wool, reeling silk, or making shoes, but the emergence of railways and other modern transport systems (Suez Canal), ports (Alexandria, Izmir, Abadan), telegraph and telephone lines and an increasing number of manufacturing plants (textile), mines and oil facilities increased the number of workers.⁶ The first decades of the 20th century also witnessed the emergence of mass urban politics, in which workers had an active part. Their struggles, often directed against the colonial structures, inspired the urban educated

³ For interpretations of the main forms of Islamism (political Islam) as populism, see Abrahamian, Ervand, “Fundamentalism or Populism.” In *Khomeinism: Essays on the Islamic Republic* (Berkeley: University of California, 1993); Colás, Alejandro, “The Re-invention of Populism: Islamist Responses to Capitalist Development in the Contemporary Maghreb,” *Historical Materialism* 12,4; Chris Harman, “The Prophet and the Proletariat,” *International Socialism Journal* 64, Autumn 1994; Jafari, Peyman “Rupture and Revolt in Iran,” *International Socialism Journal* 124, Autumn 2009.

⁴ Zürcher, Erik-Jan, “Ottoman Sources of Kemalist Thought.” In Elisabeth Özdalga (ed.), *Late Ottoman Society: Intellectual Legacy*. New York: Routledge, 2005.

⁵ Atabaki, Touraj and Zürcher, Erik-Jan (eds.), *Men of Order: Authoritarian Modernization under Atatürk and Reza Shah*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2004.

⁶ See for instance Quataert, Donald, *Manufacturing in the Ottoman Empire and Turkey, 1500-1950*. Albany: State University of New York Press, 1994; Quataert, Donald and Zürcher, Erik-Jan (eds.), *Workers and the Working Class in the Ottoman Empire and the Turkish Republic*. London: I.B. Tauris, 1995.

elite to approach workers as potential members of a modern nation, if they were provided proper education.

The first significant strikes appeared in this period, for instance between 1908 and 1910 in Egypt by tramway workers and railway workshop workers⁷ and the first modern trade unions were organized, for instance the Anatolian Railway workers' union and Tehran's print shop workers union, both established in 1907. Nationalist intellectuals and political leaders welcomed these struggles, as they provided ammunition against foreign powers, for instance during the Arab Revolt of 1936-38 in Palestine.⁸ Although liberal nationalism had a great influence on these movements, particularly in Egypt through the Nationalist Party in the 1910s and the Wafd Party in the 1920s and 1930s,⁹ social radicalism had a significant presence as well. Thus many strikes were not only targeting foreign domination, but also domestic tyranny and social injustices, and socialists and communists were at the heart of the emerging workers' organizations.

Many of the trade unions were initiated by communist workers and intellectuals, and their influence increased following the Russian Revolution. In the late 1920s, for instance, the communist activist Yusuf Eftekhari helped to form a number of underground cells among the 11,000 oil workers of the Anglo-Persian Oil Company in Abadan. Despite arrests and repression, oil workers protested on May Day 1929 demanding higher wages, shorter hours, and recognition of their trade union. A general strike on 4 May was repressed, but as Stephanie Cronin has argued, it signified the arrival of a new social force in Iranian politics, demonstrating the potency of a new type of protest, the industrial strike.¹⁰ Strikes like this linked social demands to nationalist aspirations of independence and development. Another important aspect of these strikes was their potential to transcend ethnic divisions and unite workers around social and anti-imperialist demands. Writing on the historiography of labour in Iraq, Eric Davis observes, "In none of the strikes and worker demonstrations that I have examined did ethnolinguistic or confessional differences play any significant role dividing worker loyalties. Indeed, Western diplomatic records, largely of worker demands, underline the tremendous amount of worker solidarity throughout strikes and demonstrations despite the use of armed force to bring them to an end."¹¹ Examples of other strikes, such as the 1946 oil strike in Abadan that was marked by ethnic tensions – instigated by the British authorities

⁷ Beinin, Joel and Lockman, Zachary, *Workers on the Nile: Nationalism, Communism, Islam and the Egyptian Working Class, 1882-1954*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1987.

⁸ For a discussion of labour activism in historic Palestine and the attempts to create unity among Jewish and Arab workers see Lockman, Zachary, *Comrades and Enemies: Arab and Jewish Workers in Palestine, 1906-1948*. Berkeley, Los Angeles and London: University of California Press, 1996.

⁹ Beinin, Joel, *Workers and Peasants in the Modern Middle East*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001, pp. 75-90.

¹⁰ Cronin, Stephanie, "Popular Politics, the New State and the Birth of the Iranian Working Class: The 1929 Abadan Oil Refinery Strike," *Middle Eastern Studies* 46,5, 2010, pp. 699-732.

¹¹ Davis, Eric, "History for the Many or History for the Few? The Historiography of the Iraqi Working Class." In *Working and Working Classes in the Middle East: Struggles, Histories, Historiographies*. Albany: State University of New York Press, 1994, p. 291.

– between Arabs and the communist led union, show class solidarity not always won the day, but it was a significant force nevertheless.¹²

By weakening and distracting the colonial powers, the Second World War created the conditions in which labour radicalism increased in the 1940s and 1950s as the following examples demonstrate: the Shubra al-Khayma textile workers' strikes in 1946 and 1951-52, the 1951 strike of the 71,000 Egyptian workers employed by the British in the Suez Canal Zone, the first industrial strike in Bahrain in the Bahrain Petroleum Company (BAPCO) in December 1943 followed by the formation of the General Trade Union a decade later, oil workers' strikes in Iran in 1946, the legalization of twelve of the sixteen trade unions in Iraq in 1944-46 followed by strikes of Iraqi rail workers in 1945 at Schalchiyya railway workshops, oil workers' strike in Kirkuk in 1946 and at the K3 pumping station near Haditha in April 1948, and the formation of the Aden Trades Union Congress in 1956 in South Yemen.¹³

The rise of nationalist populism in the 1950s and 1960s in the Middle East was the continuation of the anti-colonial struggles of the previous decades as members of the new middle class, often in military uniforms, attempted to realize national independence through post-colonial state-building. Nationalist populism, however, was also in a way the recognition of the power of the working class and at the same time an attempt to neutralize its social radicalism by denying working class subjectivity and instead promoting the notion of the "people."¹⁴ Inspired by the Soviet Union's the state capitalist path to industrialization, nationalist populist leaders combined anti-imperialism with state-led industrialization and social reforms that aligned workers and landless peasants with the state bureaucracy.

These political projects, referred to as "Arab socialism," became manifest in Egypt under Gamal Abdel Nasser, in Syria under Ba'athist rule after 1963, in Iraq under the Free Officers following their military overthrow of the monarchy in 1958 and then the Ba'athist rule after 1968. Post-colonial, nationalist, authoritarian populist regimes were also established in Tunisia and Algeria, although in weaker forms, and even the Shah of Iran was developing his own populist style in the 1960s through what he called the "Revolution of the Shah and the People" (White Revolution). While banning independent trade unions, these regimes promised to further the cause of workers through the strategy of import-substitution. The incorporation of trade unions could go very far, as in Tunisia where Ahmad Ben Salah, the main union secretary general, became minister of economy

¹² On the 1946 Abadan strike see Abrahamian, Ervand, *Iran Between Two Revolutions*. Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press, 1982, pp. 361-62.

¹³ On Egyptian workers' protests in this period, see Beinin and Lockman, *Workers on the Nile*, pp. 285-363. On the 1946 Abadan strike see Atabaki, Touraj, "Chronicle of a Strike Foretold: Abadan, July 1946" (forthcoming); On Iraq's oil strikes see Batatu, Hanna, *The Old Social Classes and the Revolutionary Movements of Iraq: A Study of Iraq's Old Landed and Commercial Classes and of Its Communists, Ba'athists, and Free Officers*. London: Saqi Books, 2004 [1978], pp.622-27.

¹⁴ Peasant revolts in a number of countries, most importantly Egypt and Syria, had the same effect.

in 1961 and “advocated imposing austerity in order to build socialism.”¹⁵ In Egypt, labour activism resurfaced in the early 1970s following Nasser’s death, but the trade union leader’s loyalty to the state maintained the corporatist break on strikes under al-Sadat. In Iran, strikes and other labour protests decreased following the crack down on the labour movement and the Left after the 1953 coup d’état against the nationalist Prime Minister Mohammad Mosaddeq, and during the economic growth and the social reforms of the 1960s. The only country going against the grain was Turkey. As Ronnie Margulies and Ergin Yildizoğlu write, “The 1960s witnessed the transformation of a young and inexperienced working class into a very militant and highly organized sector. The number of unionized workers increased in leaps and bounds, reaching the one-million mark at the end of the decade. Strikes involved larger numbers of workers and were more prolonged, particularly in the late 1960s and throughout the 1970s.”¹⁶

The nationalist populist regime’s subordination of independent labour movements in this period didn’t meet any significant resistance from the Stalinist parties that due to their two-stages theory conceived these regimes as the first necessary stage and deferred socialist class struggle to later. By the 1970s, however, these regimes were stagnating or falling into crisis due to the limitations of import-substitution development. The demise of secular nationalist populism and communism opened up a bigger space for the growth of Islamist movements that had emerged in the late 19th and early 20th century mainly as reactions to imperialism. Just as the nationalist populist movements, Islamist were forced to recognised the significance of the working class, but they too tried to subordinate the labour movement and neutralize its radicalism by denying its autonomy and subsuming it under the Islamic “ummah.”

In Egypt, for instance, Muslim Brothers were involved in the formation of the Shubra al-Khayma Mechanized Textile Workers’ Union in the late 1930s. In the 1940s they started to pay more attention to social issues and established the Workers’ Section of the Society of Muslim Brothers to exert more direct influence in the workers’ movement.¹⁷ While promising to establish social justice and improve workers’ living standards, the Muslim Brothers denied class-based politics. Ayatollah Khomeini, who stood at the head of the Islamist current in the Iranian Revolution and founded the Islamic Republic, explicitly adopted a class-struggle and social justice vocabulary, using terms such as “mostazafan”, the downtrodden, to refer to a mixed group that included not only the poor and workers, but also pious merchants. But in Khomeini’s Islamist populism that shaped the state-society relations in the 1980s in Iran, workers were praised and promised benefits, but they were denied the right to organize independently. The similarity with nationalist populist approach to labour activism doesn’t stop here. The Islamic Republic of Iran were trying to follow the path of import-substitution and state-led development,

¹⁵ Joel Beinin, *Workers and Peasants in the Modern Middle East*, p.137.

¹⁶ Margulies, Ronnie and Yildizoğlu, Ergin, “Trade Unions and Turkey’s Working Class,” *Merip Reports* 121, February 1984, pp.15-31.

¹⁷ Beinin and Lockman, *Workers on the Nile*, pp.363-394.

before introducing liberalization policies from the 1990s onwards, and marginalizing even the recognized labour organizations.

From neoliberalism to the Arab Revolutions

If nationalist and Islamist narratives obscured the importance of labour activism, the rise of neoliberalism since the 1980s has tried to obliterate the labour movement socially, organizationally and discursively. The *infitah* policies adopted in Egypt in 1974 signalled the introduction of privatization and liberalization in all most all Middle Eastern countries in the following two decades; in Tunisia and Morocco in the late 1970s as the government enthusiastically adopted the “structural adjustment programmes” of the IMF and the World Bank, in Turkey after the military coup in 1980, and in Iran from the early 1990s onwards. These policies that unravelled the populist arrangements and undermined the position of even the yellow trade unions were met by labour protests, which were subsequently repressed.

At the same time, the developments of the previous decades had started to reconfigure the working class. Most importantly, rapid urbanization expanded the shantytowns and the numbers of people working in the “informal sector” as unemployment, underemployment, precarious labour relations, and unpaid labour increased. These workers lacked the experience of collective organization and rarely joined trade unions. This reconfiguration was also prompted by the expansion of the service sector and the stagnation of the industries, which led to a slight increase of female labour. The possibility of labour migration, induced by the oil-boom after 1973, formed another obstacle to labour activism. In the mid-1980s, there were over 5 million migrant Arab workers in the Persian Gulf countries and some 2.5 million North Africans were employed in Europe.¹⁸

As neoliberalism marched on in the 1990s and 2000s, class politics became out of vogue and the importance of labour activism was widely denied. Labour unions were at best seen as civil society organizations that should promote workers’ rights within the free market. The Arab Revolutions of 2011, however, have brought labour activism back into the spotlights, not only due to important role they played in the Egyptian and Tunisian revolutions, but also due to a broader return of the “social question” that has preceded these revolutions. One can for instance point to the revival of labour activism in Iran since the early 2000s, and the increasing attention for the plight of migrant workers in the Persian Gulf countries and the deepening of social inequalities globally and in the Middle East.¹⁹

¹⁸ Beinin, *Workers and Peasants in the Modern Middle East*, p. 151.

¹⁹ On Iran, see Andreas, Malm and Esmailian, Shora, *Iran on the Brink: Rising Workers and Threats of War* (London, Ann Arbor, MI: Pluto, 2007); Moghissi, Haideh and Rahnema, Saeed, “The Working Class and the Islamic State in Iran,” in *Socialist Register* 2011, pp.197-218; Sina

The Arab Revolutions have stimulated a number of new publications on labour activism in the Middle East. In the opening article of this special issue of *Workers of the World*, Brecht de Smet reviews a number of publications centred around the issues of social class and labour activism in the Middle East, reflecting on the revolutions that swept the region in 2011. In his timely article on the Tunisian General Union of Labour, Mohamed-Salah Omri counters the assumption that “the Arab world was incapable of producing agency, which is neither military tribal, factional, or in the form of exceptional individuals whether secular or religious,” and sets out to explain the relatively successful course of the Tunisian revolution, which he partly contributes to the significant role played by the trade union.

Labour activism, of course, most often comes in small acts and non-revolutionary situations. In an ethnographic study of the Jordan Phosphate Mines Company, Claudie Fioronie explores the motivations behind workers’ protests, tracing their roots to their everyday experience in the workplace. Finally, Derek Alan Ide provides a more historical perspective, looking at two episodes of repression of communist workers and party members under Nasser’s nationalist populism, highlighting the problematic relationship that existed between Nasserism and communism in Egypt.

Together, these articles remind us that labour activism has played and continues to play an important role in the Middle East and North Africa and that it provides the best hope to challenge neoliberalism, foreign domination and ethno-religious sectarianism.